
2 **Abstract**

Intermodal freight transport consists of using different modes of transport without changing the load unit. This results in a significant reduction in the time that goods spend at intermodal terminals, where transshipment takes place. Drayage refers to the transport of freight on trucks among intermodal terminals, depots, customers and suppliers. In spite of the fact that drayage only represents between 5 and 10 percent of total distance, it may amount up to more than 30 percent of the total costs. The aim of this work is to study drayage operations. First, an extensive literature review is undertaken. Since the intermodal transport chain can become more efficient by means of a proper organisation of the drayage movements, the optimization of the daily drayage problem has been identified as one of the main ways of reducing the drayage cost and improving intermodal operations. On this problem, the lack of a common benchmark has hindered reaching further conclusions from all the research carried out. Therefore, this paper proposes a common framework and presents a generalized formulation of the problem, which allows modeling most drayage policies, with the limitation of only considering one-container problems. Results show that flexible tasks in the repositioning of empty containers as well as soft time windows can reduce the operating costs and facilitate the management of drayage companies. This work may help consider adequate policies regarding drayage operations in intermodal terminals.

3 *Keywords:*

4 Drayage, Intermodality, Benchmark, Soft Time Windows, Flexible Tasks

5 **1. Introduction**

6 Nowadays, long chains of transport are responsible for connecting customers around the world, eliminating
7 geographic barriers between production and consumption. This has fostered globalization, which requires
8 efficient transport management.

9 Among the modes of transport, maritime transport is the most common option for long-distance journeys.
10 However, being lacking in flexibility, it is necessary to synchronize maritime shipments, port-to-port, with
11 other means of transport, such as rail and road transport. This concept is known as multimodal transport.

12 Among the different methods of good transportation, the largest growth occurs in intermodal transport,
13 a type of multimodality. It consists of using different means of transport to carry a load unit, usually
14 containers. This feature allows for a reduction of the time that goods must spend in intermodal terminals
15 because operations of loading and unloading of goods from one container to another are replaced by operations
16 of collecting and delivering containers between different means of transport.

17 With all this, this paper focuses on drayage operations. These operations usually take place at the
18 beginning and the end of the intermodal transport chain and include the collection and delivery of empty
19 and loaded containers in depots, terminals and customers facilities. These containers are carried among
20 different locations in the area of an intermodal terminal by road.

21 Even though drayage operations only represent a small percentage of the total distance in the intermodal
22 chain, these amount to a high percentage of the total cost (Spasovic and Morlok, 1993; Escudero-Santana,
23 2013). The optimization of drayage operations represents an effective way to foster intermodal transport.
24 Moreover, given that drayage movements usually take place near urban areas, adequate planning of drayage
25 operations results in an indirect improvement of the environmental conditions and other external costs (Chen
26 et al., 2013; Demir et al., 2015).

27 There are several types of drayage movements. The main movements are the freight importation and
28 exportation orders, where the load unit (usually a container) is moved between the terminal and the customer
29 or vice versa. In these instances, the container could be either full or empty, but the origin and destination
30 of the movement are known (well-defined orders). Another possible type of drayage order is the repositioning
31 of empty containers. This is necessary for the logistic activities of different customers. In this case, the
32 movement could be carried out directly from or to the depot, known as direct-depot movement. In addition,
33 empty containers that need to be withdrawn from a customer can be transferred directly to another customer
34 in need for them. This is referred to as turn-street movement. Thus, there exist different possibilities for
35 fulfilling the requirements, and some aspects of the orders are therefore flexible.

36 These orders are carried out by trucks, which are composed of tractors, trailers chassis and containers.
37 Trucks perform two fundamental operations, collection and delivery of containers. A basic order usually
38 involves a collection operation, a displacement, and a delivery operation.

39 Additionally, more complex orders are possible. As seen above, the need to have containers available at
40 different points at certain times makes the transport of empty containers essential. Thus, sometimes it is
41 necessary to alternate tasks of delivery and collection of containers at a given point. This may be caused
42 by the client lacking sufficient space to store containers or a lack of additional containers to make other
43 shipments. Two solutions are feasible: the driver stands by the container while it is unloaded, which is
44 referred to as stay-with policy, or the driver leaves after the delivery of the container, known as drop and pick
45 policy. In this case, an unloaded truck (not necessarily the vehicle that delivered the goods) will be required
46 once the container is empty.

47 The daily drayage problem (DDP) has been the most studied problem of this area of research. This
48 problem can be stated as follows (Jula et al., 2005): a set of containers needs to be moved in the area of
49 an intermodal terminal by a trucking company. A set of trucks, initially located at the company depot, is
50 deployed to move these containers among the depot, customers and terminals. Associated with each container
51 there are time windows imposed by the customer and the terminal. The DDPTW is a relaxation of the vehicle
52 routing problem with time windows (VRPTW). However, the procedures developed for the VRPTW are not

53 well suited for the relaxation of the problem (Dumas et al., 1995).

54 Many authors have contributed to this area in order to address the necessity for specific methods. After an
55 extensive literature review on drayage operation optimization using mathematical methods, we have found
56 out that most of the works presented focus on the efficiency of their approaches. Besides, there exists a
57 lack of a common framework or benchmark to develop these studies, which makes it hard to draw general
58 conclusions.

59 Therefore, it is necessary to create a common benchmark to study the effect of different policies regard-
60 ing the management of drayage operations. This work undertakes that goal and proposes a generalized
61 formulation and benchmark for the comparison of different policies.

62 In addition to the proposed common framework, this paper provides an extensive review and analysis of
63 how certain policies can influence the performance of haulage operations. Two policies have been studied: the
64 effect of flexible tasks in the repositioning of empty containers and the effect of allowing soft time windows
65 (a research angle neglected so far). The study presents several simplifications. Noticeably, that a truck can
66 only carry one container at a time.

67 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 identifies the methodology used in the review
68 process. Section 3 provides a review of related works, identifying the contribution of each paper. Section 4
69 presents a deep formulation and description of the problem. Section 5 analyses the experiments conducted
70 in previous studies and establishes the proposed benchmark. Section 6 discusses the experimental results.
71 Finally, section 7 concludes the paper.

72 **2. Review methodology**

73 The following sections focus on the literature relating to drayage operation optimization using mathe-
74 matical approaches. Qualitative studies are not covered in this study. The search was conducted on several
75 library databases (Web of Science, Scopus and IEEE Xplore) through the insertion of some related keywords:
76 drayage, VRP full load, intermodal hinterland, truck intermodal, container truck, and haulage. Selected pa-
77 pers from the searches were analysed and classified. The references of each paper were examined to find new
78 related works.

79 This search method allowed us to cover a great variety of journal and conference papers. Some conference
80 papers were improved by their author and subsequently published in a journal; in these cases, the review was
81 limited to the most recent paper.

82 In total, 77 works have been examined, coming from journals such as Transportation Research (A, B,
83 C, D, E), Transportation Research Record, European Journal of Operational Research, International Trans-
84 actions in Operational Research, Operations Research Letters, OR Spectrum, IIE Transactions, Advanced
85 Engineering Informatics, Computers and Industrial Engineering, and International Journal of Production
86 Economics. Figure 1 shows the number of papers published in each journal. In section 3, these studies are

87 classified and summarized according to their main line of action to improve the drayage. As we can observe
 88 in Figure 2, the tendency of number of publications per year is increasing.

Figure 1: Number of papers published in each journal

89 Because most of the papers present an operational perspective and focus on the optimization of routes
 90 (usually referred to as the daily drayage problem, DDP), these works were studied more extensively. These
 91 papers are classified according to several characteristics of the problem (consideration of empty containers,
 92 consideration of time windows, possibility of flexible or complex tasks, dynamism or uncertainty considera-
 93 tion) and some characteristics of the solution methodology (formulation, method, etc.).

Figure 2: Number of papers per year

94 Other relevant information is the classification of the different instances or benchmarks used to validate
 95 these works. Because no common benchmark exists, an important aspect is to know if the studies are
 96 reproducible. Thus, we have identified the works whose instances are published or are at least reproducible.
 97 These are located in section 5.

98 There also exist some studies covering issues similar to the daily drayage problem. We have considered
 99 conducting a brief review of these works, since some of their conclusions could be useful for future works

100 related to drayage. The search terms for these works are truck trailer and swap body.

101 **3. Extensive literature review**

102 As mentioned above, even though the drayage operations only represent a small percentage of the total
103 distance of the intermodal chain, the optimization of these operations is a very important issue due to the
104 fact that these operations represent a high percentage of the total cost.

105 The first studies regarding drayage operations dealt with the issue from a strategic perspective. They
106 focused on the effect of different measures, decisions or regulations on the performance of the total supply
107 chain and its potential market; the main items studied have been marked below in bold. Subsequent studies
108 delved into operational aspects of drayage management, establishing approaches of planning daily operations
109 that would allow to achieve the lines of action of previous studies.

110 Fowkes et al. (1991) was the first study to underline the implication of drayage operations in the total
111 intermodal chain. It examined the relative **position of both origin and destination regarding inter-**
112 **modal terminal**, developing a cost model, and proved that it has implications over the profitability of the
113 global transport. The combination of this cost model with a stated preference experiment determine the
114 market share respect to road transport. In this line of research, Nierat (1997) studied the market area of a
115 rail-truck terminal. The result of this study concluded the notable effect that the relative localization of the
116 customer respect to terminal has over market area. Since an operational perspective, Taylor et al. (2002)
117 studied two approaches of terminal selection, whose objective is to increase the efficiency and profitability of
118 intermodal transport.

119 Morlok and Spasovic (1995) studied which factors influence drayage operation costs and established
120 strategies to reduce the costs. These strategies, destined for both public and private sectors, are based on
121 several measures: centralized management of drayage, the use of new technologies, adequate marketing and
122 price selection, increase in terminal capacity, improvement in the access to it, and adequate land use policies.

123 Based on a previous study (Spasovic and Morlok, 1993), they considered that **centralized management**
124 **of drayage operations**, among different carriers, can reduce the necessary time to perform the drayage
125 tasks and yield substantial cost savings in the range of 30% to 45%. More recently, Sterzik et al. (2015)
126 demonstrated the benefit of the cooperative use of empty containers. In addition to cost savings, adequate
127 planning of drayage tasks can increase the area of influence of a terminal. The **increase in the occupation**
128 **factor of the trucks or in the number of daily tasks per driver** is regarded by Nierat (1997) as
129 responsible for a growth of this area. The advantage of an efficient management of the drayage operations is
130 the main topic of the majority of the mathematical studies related to drayage. This topic will be the central
131 issue of this paper, so this will be studied in a separate epigraph.

132 As noted by Morlok and Spasovic (1995), some **regulation measures** could influence the final drayage
133 cost. A particular case is studied by Cheung et al. (2008), who analysed various historical regulations imposed
134 by the Hong Kong government on drayage operation within China. They studied the 4up-4down policy versus

135 other more flexible policies, such as 2up-2down or a free policy. Under the 4up-4down policy, when a quadruple
136 of driver+tractor+trailer+container goes from Hong Kong to China, the exact same quadruple must return
137 to Hong Kong together. In the 2up-2down policy, only the driver and tractor are inseparable. They conclude
138 that there are losses of benefits due to this restriction and suggest a relaxation of these measures. In this
139 line, Shiri and Huynh (2017) developed a new model of a free policy to assess the effectiveness of different
140 chassis supply models currently in use in the U.S. on productivity and air emissions.

141 **New technology investments** help to reduce drayage costs. These technologies could focus on providing
142 improved information (Huynh and Zumerchik, 2010) or facilitating the movement of loads (such as the work
143 of Shintani et al. (2010), who studied the impact of foldable containers on container fleet management costs).

144 Because of the high volume of drayage trucks arriving at container terminals, the trucks often experience
145 significant **delays at the terminal gates** or inside them. The effects of new technologies to reduce these
146 delays are another important aspect to consider. Huynh and Zumerchik (2010) researched how automated
147 transfer management systems (ATMS) can be combined with intelligent transport system (ITS) technologies
148 and e-business environments of the terminals to reduce the dwell time of trucks in the terminal. This paper
149 specifically investigates the effect of priority rules for stacking containers into the ATMS to improve port
150 drayage operations. Namboothiri and Erera (2008) and Zehendner and Feillet (2014) studied the impact of
151 appointment-based access control systems on the productivity of drayage firms. Minh and Huynh (2014)
152 modelled the terminal gates by means of queuing theory to determine the most effective layout for marine
153 container terminals. Finally, Huynh et al. (2016) and Zhang and Zhang (2017) examined the state of the
154 art and the state of practice for truck appointment systems. Zhao and Goodchild (2011) underlined the
155 importance of the **reliability of travel time** and developed a method to predict it. Marković et al. (2014)
156 described a probabilistic subproblem of the drayage operation in a real environment where there is uncertainty.
157 Their study attempted to recommend a departure time for a truck, with that being the objective of the
158 minimization of the operating cost. They searched for this time through a local search and a hybrid genetic
159 algorithm. The work developed by Chen and Yang (2010) solved the previous problem of determination
160 of the time windows. Chen et al. (2013) developed a queuing-based bi-objective model for optimizing the
161 truck arrival pattern and reducing truck emissions at container terminals. Escudero et al. (2009), Escudero
162 et al. (2011b), Escudero et al. (2011a), Escudero et al. (2013), You et al. (2016) and You and Ritchie (2017)
163 demonstrated the usefulness of GPS technology in analysing drayage truck tours and thus **improving the**
164 **information available** to the solver. Wasesa et al. (2017) developed a seaport service rate prediction system
165 that could help drayage operators improve their predictions of the duration of the pick-up/delivery operations
166 at a seaport.

167 *3.1. daily drayage problem*

168 Morlok and Spasovic (1995) established centralized management of drayage as a critical aspect for the
169 profitability of intermodal transport. Several years elapsed between that publication and the study of Wang
170 and Regan (2002), which could be considered the first work from an operational perspective and focused on

171 the daily drayage problem (DDP). A considerable number of studies now focus on the daily drayage problem,
172 sometimes referred to by other names, as a full-load vehicle scheduling problem or container drayage problem.
173 The increase in the number of publications coincides with the importance that intermodal transport has
174 achieved in political institutions. A brief overview of the main contributions of every work is presented
175 below.

176 Within the PDD, we can find works focused on different aspects of the problem. There are works that
177 consider a single terminal, while others consider several; studies where the size of the containers is unique
178 and others where different sizes are considered; and works that only consider well-defined orders and others
179 where the tasks can be flexible, especially in the case of empty containers. At this point, we have grouped
180 the works reviewed based on these criteria.

181 *3.1.1. Well-defined orders of loaded or empty containers*

182 The daily drayage problem with well-defined orders was the first problem studied. Wang and Regan (2002)
183 adapted the pickup and delivery problem to the specific operations in rail or maritime intermodal terminals.
184 They model the daily drayage problem as a multiple travelling salesman problem with time window constraints
185 (am-TSPTW) and present an iterative solution approach where two versions of the problem (over-constrained
186 and under-constrained) are solved by a specific time window partitioning approach. The over-constrained
187 method provides a feasible solution, while the gap between the two solutions allows for a decision regarding
188 the stop criterion. Cheung and Hang (2003) developed a deterministic model with time windows that is
189 then solved by means of the discretization of time. They incorporated the concept of fictitious tasks, which
190 is used to simulate restrictions of the vehicles. Jula et al. (2005) solved a problem with time windows at
191 the origin and the destination by using three solution approaches: (a) an exact method based on dynamic
192 programming, (b) a hybrid methodology consisting of dynamic programming to generate feasible solutions
193 in conjunction with genetic algorithms, and (c) a heuristic insertion method. They model every possible
194 well-defined single movement of a container in a metropolitan area. Caris and Janssens (2009) proposed
195 a two-phase insertion heuristic to construct an initial solution that is then improved with a local search
196 heuristic. Following this work, Caris and Janssens (2010) included a deterministic annealing algorithm. In
197 Escudero-Santana et al. (2015), a metaheuristic based on viral systems was applied. Imai et al. (2007)
198 developed a subgradient heuristic based on a Lagrangian relaxation. In this line, Di Francesco et al. (2019)
199 present theoretical formulations and prove that its continuous relaxation admits integer optimal solutions.

200 The movement of empty containers is another issue of great interest. Jula et al. (2006) studied the
201 movement of empty container in the Los Angeles and Long Beach (LA/LB) port area and developed a two-
202 phase optimization technique. This paper, which could be considered the first work focused on the drayage
203 of only empty containers, uses several case studies based on current and projected demand to evaluate two
204 different policies: street-turn and depot-direct. Chang et al. (2008) followed the previous paper and proposed
205 a heuristic method. Deidda et al. (2008) and Furió et al. (2013) analysed the effects of the street-turn policy
206 in real environments.

207 *3.1.2. Integration of both loaded container movement and empty containers repositioning*

208 Special attention has been paid to integrate the allocation of empty containers and the routing in drayage
209 operations. Ileri et al. (2006) considered several task types, both simple and combined, and studied the costs
210 involved in drayage operations. In combined tasks, two operation modes are considered: drop-and-hook,
211 where the driver drops one container and hooks to another, and live, where the driver must wait while the
212 container is being loaded or unloaded. They solved the problem via a column generation method. Even
213 though there exist empty containers movements, these are well-defined tasks. A related problem was solved
214 by Xue et al. (2014) and Xue et al. (2015). They examined a drayage problem in which a tractor can
215 be detached from its companion trailer and assigned to a new task. A tabu search algorithm and an ant
216 colony optimization method were proposed, respectively. Song et al. (2017) also studied a drayage problem
217 under a resource-separation mode; in addition, they considered the case in which some empty containers
218 should return to the depot for maintenance. A branch-and-price-and-cut algorithm was proposed to solve
219 it. Caballini et al. (2016) proposed an optimization model for the cooperative planning of multiple truck
220 carrier operations to maximize the total profit derived from their cooperation. A compensation mechanism
221 is introduced to motivate carriers to share their trips.

222 Some studies add the possibility of flexible tasks, since the origins and destinations of some movements
223 can be chosen from a set of possible nodes. This feature is particularly interesting since it allows flexibility
224 in the origin or destination of empty containers. In this line, Smilowitz (2006) studied the problem as an
225 am-TSPTW with flexible tasks, which let him model a free policy of container repositioning. Therefore, turn-
226 street and depot-direct movements can be considered for every empty container requirement. The possible
227 executions of each flexible task are limited by the distance between nodes. Thus, turn-street movements
228 are only carried out within a feasible geographical region. The solution approach developed to solve this
229 problem includes column generation embedded in a branch-and-bound process. This work was improved
230 by Francis et al. (2007), who introduced a variable radius method to define possible executions of flexible
231 tasks. Zhang et al. (2011a) extended these previous works and added dynamic requests of tasks throughout
232 the day. They embedded a branch and price in a rolling horizon method. Coslovich et al. (2006) described
233 a fleet management problem focused on the minimization of the present and future operation costs. They
234 formulated an integer programming model and proposed a Lagrangian relaxation, decomposing the problem
235 into three subproblems: task pairing, resource assignment and container repositioning.

236 *3.1.3. Multi-depot and multi-terminal*

237 Reinhardt et al. (2016) presented a generalized formulation of the DDP in which flexible tasks and
238 multiple depots are considered. They established a novel constraint to balance the empty container depot
239 levels. By exploring the fact that the number of possible routes in the considered case is quite limited, they
240 demonstrated that the model can be solved within a minute by use of an exact method based on column
241 enumeration. Zhang et al. (2009) formulated the problem as an am-TSPTW with multiple depots and a single
242 terminal and used a reactive tabu search to solve it. This problem was expanded by Zhang et al. (2010),

243 who used a window-partition-based method inspired by Wang and Regan (2002). The problem defined in
244 Zhang et al. (2010) was solved by Sterzik et al. (2015) using a cost-saving heuristic and a tabu search; their
245 objective was to demonstrate the benefits of cooperative use of an empty container. Zhang et al. (2011b)
246 limited the number of empty containers in the depot (even though this problem only considers a depot and
247 a terminal, it is computationally more complex). A similar problem is solved in Zhang et al. (2020), which
248 propose a large neighborhood search algorithm. Nossack and Pesch (2013) presented a new formulation for
249 the truck scheduling problem based on a full-truckload pickup and the delivery problem with time windows
250 and propose a two-stage heuristic approach. The results of computational experiments indicated that their
251 2-stage heuristic outperforms the method applied by Zhang et al. (2010) in terms of computational efficiency.

252 Following their previous line of work, Braekers et al. (2013) formulated an am-TSPTW to solve the
253 DDPTW and empty container repositioning and proposed two methods: a sequential method, where empty
254 container allocations are determined before vehicle routes are created, and an integrated method. Both
255 methods are based on simulated annealing. They concluded that the integrated approach clearly outperforms
256 the sequential one. Braekers et al. (2014) extended the previous work from a bi-objective perspective, and
257 three solution algorithms were proposed: an iterative method, a two-phase deterministic annealing algorithm,
258 and a two-phase hybrid deterministic annealing and tabu search algorithm. Their comparison determined
259 that the best results are obtained by the last one.

260 Sun et al. (2014) described a solution method using a set-partitioning formulation and column-generation
261 heuristic and reported on a large-scale implementation. They focused on real-world implementation details,
262 including: (1) fast solution times to support near-real-time re-solving in the face of constantly changing data,
263 (2) adjustments to account for traffic congestion and other operational considerations, and (3) integration
264 with a commercial transportation management system to provide real-time data to the optimizer and to send
265 solution recommendations to a driver-assignment process. This was used in large metropolitan hub areas,
266 such as Chicago and Los Angeles.

267 Some works focus on the necessity of transfers among terminals. This is what occurs when intermodal
268 containers need to be transferred from one terminal to another to continue the shipment. Chung et al.
269 (2007) presented heuristic algorithms to solve a real-world example, the data set for which was collected
270 from a container trucking company in Korea. Pazour and Neubert (2013) also developed a heuristic solution
271 approach. They illustrated how this problem has special characteristics that require a novel methodology.
272 Sterzik and Kopfer (2013) developed a tabu search to solve a problem that also considers empty container
273 repositioning and several container sizes. All of these methods try to cover the maximum number of loads
274 with the minimum empty moves. Bai et al. (2015) resolved a specific definition of the drayage problem where
275 several labour shifts are considered. A set-covering model is formulated to solve the problem.

276 *3.1.4. Multi-size container load*

277 In addition to Sterzik and Kopfer (2013), other works have also considered different container sizes. Lai
278 et al. (2013) addressed a problem in which trucks can carry one or two containers. They determined an initial

279 solution by a variant of the Clarke-and-Wright algorithm and improved it by a sequence of local search phases.
280 Zhang et al. (2015) and Funke and Kopfer (2016) formulated an extension of their previous works, modelling
281 different types of containers. In Zhang et al. (2015), three tree search procedures and an improved reactive
282 tabu search algorithm were designed to solve the problem with time windows not considered. In Funke
283 and Kopfer (2016), a mixed-integer linear program was presented using two alternative objective functions:
284 minimization of the total travel distance and minimization of the total operation time of the trucks. In
285 Vidović et al. (2016), a multisize container drayage problem with time windows was modelled as a multiple
286 matching problem and formulated as a mixed integer linear program model. To solve larger-sized problems,
287 they proposed a variable neighbourhood search. Ritzinger et al. (2017) developed a variable neighbourhood
288 search to solve a problem that considers the compatibility between container types and trailer types. Daham
289 et al. (2017) presented a drayage problem that considers different sizes of containers, containers with multiple
290 customer locations as its receivers, and weight constraints. They solved the problem by means of an exact
291 method. Ghezelsöflu et al. (2018) propose a set-covering formulation for a drayage problem with single and
292 double container loads. Real data of a carrier are used in the experimentation.

293 Since technologies of foldable container have almost matured, some studies are considering this containers
294 into drayage service scheduling. Zhang et al. (2018) solve the foldable container drayage problem by means
295 of a reactive tabu search. The results appoint to a saving of approximately 10% on transportation compared
296 to the use of standard containers.

297 *3.1.5. Terminal appointment and long-haul integration*

298 Some works study the integrated scheduling of drayage operation and long-haul transportation. Using the
299 data set generated by Zhang et al. (2009), Wang and Yun (2013) introduced the possibility of rail transporta-
300 tion and developed a hybrid tabu search to solve a mixed-integer programming model. Pérez Rivera and Mes
301 (2019) design a simulation-based approach to integrate a MILP model for scheduling drayage operations and
302 a Markov Decision Process model for scheduling long-haul transport in the context of synchromodal trans-
303 port. Heggen et al. (2019) develop a large neighbourhood search heuristic to solve the integrated problem.
304 Fan et al. (InPress) present an genetic algorithm.

305 Shiri and Huynh (2016) addressed the challenge posed to drayage firms of having to make appointments
306 at terminals in advance. In this emerging practice, drayage firms need to make scheduling decisions while
307 complying with the terminal-specified truck appointment system. They modelled the empty container allo-
308 cation problem, vehicle routing problem and appointment booking problem in an integrated manner using a
309 mixed-integer programming model. The integrated optimization model was solved by a reactive tabu search
310 algorithm combined with a greedy algorithm. Torkjazi et al. (2018) present an approach for designing a Truck
311 Appointment System (TAS) intended to serve both the maritime container terminal operator and drayage
312 operators.

313 3.1.6. *Stochastic*

314 Other studies have also considered stochastic characteristics of the problem. These considerations ap-
315 peared in the second part of the work of Cheung and Hang (2003), who solved it with a rolling window
316 heuristic (being the first work with stochastic considerations). Cheung et al. (2005) considered the same
317 problem and solved it by means of a labelling method. In both studies, randomness only affected the dura-
318 tion of the tasks, not the displacement time among different tasks. Escudero et al. (2009) and Escudero et al.
319 (2011b) presented evolutionary algorithms to solve a problem with stochastic transit time. These studies
320 were improved in Escudero et al. (2011a) and Escudero et al. (2013), where heuristic (based on Caris and
321 Janssens (2009)) and genetic algorithms were implemented to solve a dynamic formulation of the problem.
322 Uncertainty in both service time and arrival time was considered in Máhr et al. (2010). They developed a
323 comparison between an on-line method and an agent-based method to solve a problem. Zhang et al. (2014)
324 developed a window-partitioning method to solve a problem with flexible orders where logistic information
325 could be updated during one time horizon. Shiri et al. (2019) present a work with stochastic packing and
326 unpacking times.

327 3.1.7. *Summary and similar problems*

328 A summary of the different operational studies listed above is shown in Table 1. This table synthesizes
329 information regarding the characteristic problem that the authors solve and the methodology of their solution.

330 Some interesting works have presented problems that are similar to the DDP, so their methods and
331 some of their conclusions could be applied to the DDP. Ball et al. (1983) could be considered the first of
332 these studies. They transformed the problem of the allocation of trailers for a chemical company into a
333 vehicle routing problem (VRP). Origin and destination of a movement are considered as a single node that
334 represents the entire movement with all the characteristics of the movement (duration, origin, destination
335 and time windows).

336 A close problem is the vehicle routing problem with full truck loads. In this problem, there are a fleet of
337 trucks, each located at one of several depots, which must serve a given number of shipments of full truckloads
338 between specified pairs of points. Its objective is to determine minimum-cost truck routes. Its difference
339 from the DDP is the absence of terminals as principal nodes of generation and attraction of flow. Some
340 outstanding studies are presented below.

341 De Meulemeester et al. (1997) and Bodin et al. (2000) applied the transformation of Ball et al. (1983)
342 but without the consideration of time windows. Arunapuram et al. (2003) developed a branch-and-bound
343 algorithm, based on column-generation, to solve an integer-programming formulation of this problem. They
344 also took into consideration the time-window constraints and waiting costs. Currie and Salhi (2003) and
345 Currie and Salhi (2004) solved the full-load, multi-terminal, vehicle scheduling problem with backhauling
346 and time windows using exact and heuristics methods and a tabu search. Gronalt et al. (2003) developed
347 four heuristics based on cost savings to solve a full-load pick-up and delivery problem with time windows.
348 Mes et al. (2007) and Mes et al. (2010) used multiagent systems to solve the problem (as in Máhr et al.

Table 1: Summary of the studies of the daily drayage problem

Paper	Problem						Method				
	Objective	TW	Empty Container	Size Container	Terminals	Uncertain	Model	Exact	Heuristic	Meta-Heuristic	
Wang and Regan (2002)	min. Dist.	y	n	1	1	no	am-TSPTW	x*	x		
Cheung and Hang (2003)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	Service times	MIP	x+			
Cheung et al. (2005)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	Service times	MIP	x+			
Jula et al. (2005)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	no	am-TSPTW	x*	x	x	Genetic algorithm
Coslovich et al. (2006)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	no	IP	x*			
Ileri et al. (2006)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	no	IP	x			
Jula et al. (2006)	min. Cost	n	y	1	1	no	IP	x			
Smilowitz (2006)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	no	IP	x			
Chung et al. (2007)	min. Cost and min. Fleet	y	n	2	m	no	am-TSPTW		x		
Francis et al. (2007)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	no	IP	x			
Imai et al. (2007)	min. Cost	n	n	1	1	no	FLPDPTW	x*			
Caris and Janssens (2009)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	no	FLPDPTW		x		
Escudero et al. (2009)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	Transit Time	am-TSPTW			x	Dynamic evolutionary algorithm
Zhang et al. (2009)	min. Time	y	y	1	1	no	am-TSPTW			x	Tabu search
Caris and Janssens (2010)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	no	FLPDPTW			x	Simulated annealing
Mahr et al. (2010)	min. Time	y	y	1	m	Service times	MIP			x	Multi agent systems
Zhang et al. (2010)	min. Time and min. Fleet	y	y	1	3	no	am-TSPTW	x*	x		
Escudero et al. (2011a)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	Transit Time	am-TSPTW		x		
Escudero et al. (2011b)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	Transit Time	am-TSPTW			x	Genetic algorithm
Zhang et al. (2011)	min. Time and min. Fleet	y	y	1	1	no	am-TSPTW				Tabu Search
Zhang et al. (2011a)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1	Online Tasks	IP	x+			
Braekers et al. (2013)	min. Cost	y	y	1	1,3	no	am-TSPTW			x	Simulated annealing
Escudero et al. (2013)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	Transit Time	am-TSPTW		x	x	Genetic algorithm
Lai et al. (2013)	min. Cost	n	y	2	1	no	MIP		x		
Nossack and Pesch (2013)	min. Time	y	y	1	m	no	FLPDPTW		x		
Pazour and Neubert (2013)	min. Dist.	n	n	1	n.i.	no	n.i.		x		
Sterzik and Kopfer (2013)	min. Time	y	y	1	m	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Wang and Yun (2013)	min. Cost	y	y	1	2	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Braekers et al. (2014)	min. Cost and min. Fleet	y	y	1	1,3	no	am-TSPTW		x	x	Simulated annealing Tabu Search
Sun et al. (2014)	min. Cost	y	y	1	2	no	MIP	x			
Xue et al. (2014)	min. Cost	n	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Zhang et al. (2014)	min. Time	y	y	1	m	Online tasks	MIP	x*			Window partition
Bai et al. (2015)	min. Dist.	y	n	1	m	no	MIP	x*			
Escudero et al. (2015)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	no	am-TSPTW			x	Viral system
Sterzik et al. (2015)	min. Time	y	y	1	m	no	IP		x	x	Tabu Search
Xue et al. (2015)	min. Cost	n	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Ant Colony
Zhang et al. (2015)	min. Time	n	y	2	1	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Caballini et al. (2016)	max. Profit	y	y	1	1	no	IP	x			
Funke and Kopfer (2016)	min. Dist. and min. Time	y	y	2	m	no	MIP	x			
Reinhant et al. (2016)	min. Cost and min. Fleet	y	y	2	m	no	IP	x			
Shiri and Huynh (2016)	min. Time	y	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Song et al. (2016)	min. Time	y	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Tabu Search
Vidovic et al. (2016)	min. Cost	y	y	2	1	no	MIP	x		x	Variable Neighbour Search
Daham et al. (2017)	min. Cost	y	y	2	1	no	MIP	x			
Ritzinger et al. (2017)	min. Cost and max. Orders	y	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Variable Neighbour Search
Zhang et al. (2018)	min. Time	y	y	F	1	no	am-TSPTW			x	Tabu Search
Torkjazi et al. (2018)	min. Cost	y	n	1	1	no	MINLP	x			
Ghezelsoufi et al. (2018)	min. Cost	y	y	2	1	no	MIP	x			
Di Francesco et al. (2019)	min. Cost	n	n	1	1	no	IP				
Shiri et al. (2019)	min. Time	y	y	1	1	Service times	MIP	x		x	Tabu Search
Heggen et al. (2019)	min. Cost	y	y	>1	m	no	am-TSP			x	Large neighbourhood search heuristic
Pérez-Rivera and Mes (2019)	min. Cost	n	y	1	1	no	MIP	x	x		
Fan et al. (In Press)	min. Cost	n	n	1	m	no	IP			x	Genetic Algorithm
Zhang et al. (2020)	min. Time and min. Fleet	y	y	1	1	no	MIP			x	Large neighbourhood search heuristic

(F) Foldable

(*) Problem relaxation

(+) Rolling horizon

349 (2010)).

350 One variation of the previously mentioned problem is the truck and trailer routing problem (TTRP). In
351 the TTRP, a fleet of trucks (considering a truck as only the tractor) and trailers serves a set of customers.
352 Some customers with accessibility constraints must be served just by truck, while others can be served either
353 by truck or by a complete vehicle. The aim is to minimize the total distance travelled to cover all tasks or to
354 minimize the use of resources. Li et al. (2016) and Neves-Moreira et al. (2016) presented review papers. Some
355 interesting articles are: Chao (2002) and Scheuerer (2006), which proposed algorithms based on tabu search;
356 Villegas et al. (2013), which proposed a two-phase matheuristic (that uses a hybrid GRASP with iterative
357 local search (ILS) in a set-partitioning formulation of the problem); Lin et al. (2009), which solved the
358 problem by means of simulated annealing; and Regnier-Coudert et al. (2016), which developed a constructive
359 heuristic to solve the problem on a real industry scenario.

360 4. Problem definition and formulation

361 Drayage tasks contemplate every container movement around a terminal by using a truck. Because
362 drayage is usually the beginning and the end of the intermodal transport chain, the main drayage orders are
363 the movements of load containers between a terminal and customers. The movement of a container from a
364 terminal to a consignee is referred to as an importation order, while the movement of a container from a
365 consignor to a terminal is referred to as an exportation order. These orders consider the collection of the
366 container in the origin, the transportation of this from the origin to the destination, and the delivery of the
367 container to the destination. Thus, two fundamental operations can be defined: requests for collection and
368 requests for delivery. For orders of importation and exportation, the operation of collection and delivery are
369 paired, and thus the origin and destination of the order are known in advance. These orders are referred to
370 as well-defined orders.

371 While these orders to load a container require having an empty container in a particular facility, com-
372plementary orders are necessary to have empty containers available at a specific time and place. In these
373orders, only the destination of the empty container is specified because the consignor requests an empty con-
374tainer, regardless of its origin. Likewise, when the containers are unloaded, the receipts sometimes require
375the withdrawal of the container. Again, the destination of these empty containers does not matter on many
376occasions. These orders of request and removal of empty containers are named flexible orders since only
377either the origin or the destination is known in advance.

378 The movement of an empty container is not always associated with flexible orders, with the ability to
379impose a specific origin and destination. In many cases, this depends on the properties of the containers
380and the necessities of the container depot for balancing of the companies. Anyway, the movement of empty
381containers must be reduced as much as possible with the objective of maximizing the transport load factor.

382 In summary, four types of orders have been defined: exportation (E), importation (I), request for an
383empty container (IE) and removal of an empty container (OE). Other authors present more complex tasks,

384 where several of these basic orders are grouped. For example, Ileri et al. (2006) presented several combined
385 tasks and distinguished between stay-with and drop-and-pick complex orders. The formulation that will be
386 presented can contemplate these combined tasks. However, without limiting the generality of the foregoing,
387 we only consider the four basic orders, since (a) every complex task can be divided into basic orders and (b)
388 the imposition of stay-with policies usually supposes suboptimal solutions.

389 All of these orders (I , E , OE , IE) must usually be performed with consideration of some temporal
390 constraints. Thus, time windows can be imposed at the origin and destination of each tasks. Depending on
391 the type of order, the temporal constraints are different.

392 In exportation orders, these constraints are more severe, as a delay in delivery of a container at the
393 terminal can mean missing the link with the main transport (train or vessel). Thus, the container has to wait
394 at the terminal until the next means of transport that can be used for the shipment. It could take hours or
395 days and may result in additional storage costs. In importation orders, there is an early time before which
396 the shipment cannot start since the container is not available.

397 In addition to these constraints, which are derived directly from the schedule of the main transportation
398 at the terminal, there are other restrictions arising from terminal storage policies. Commonly, the terminal
399 provides time windows within which it is possible to pick up or deliver a container without any additional
400 cost. In export operations, delivering the goods before the time window carries a cost storage imposed by
401 the terminal managers, since the container should wait at the terminal before being loaded into the vessel or
402 train. Collection of a container outside the time window in import tasks assumes a similar cost for the same
403 reasons.

404 In the customers facilities, time-window constraints could be contemplated as well. For example, if an
405 empty container needs to be loaded and then sent to the terminal, this empty container must be in the facility
406 before a required time. In the case of removing an empty container, a temporal limitation can be imposed
407 due to the necessity of space.

408 This peculiarity allows the problem to be defined as a DDPTW, where there are several
409 orders or tasks that should be covered with a combination of vehicles within certain time windows. The
410 problem is to assign each task to a vehicle so that the generated costs are minimized.

411 Between the different costs that must be minimized, the first distinction appears between fixed costs and
412 variable costs. Fixed costs mainly include the salaries of drivers and the depreciation of vehicles. Among the
413 variable costs are those that depend on the distance travelled, such as fuel costs. There are also other costs
414 in drayage problems, which are the costs of penalization, which are supported when the truck violates any
415 restrictions involving compensation.

416 *4.1. Modelling of the problem*

417 Let $i \in \mathcal{O}$ be an order. Each order is associated with several parameters that define it.

- 418 • The origin where the order begins to develop, o_i .

- 419 • The destination where the order concludes, d_i .
- 420 • The service times in the origin and destination, s_i^o and s_i^d , which are the times for loading and unloading
421 the container.
- 422 • Times windows in origin and destination, $[E_i^o, L_i^o]$ and $[E_i^d, L_i^d]$, which are the intervals of time in which
423 the order should begin at the origin or at the destination to avoid extra costs.

424 Because four basic orders exist, the set \mathcal{O} has been divided into four subsets: importation orders \mathcal{O}^I ,
425 exportation orders \mathcal{O}^E , inbound empty containers \mathcal{O}^{IE} and outbound empty containers \mathcal{O}^{OE} . Subsets \mathcal{O}^I
426 and \mathcal{O}^E are well-defined orders, so all their parameters are known in advance. In importation orders, the
427 origin is located at the terminal, \dot{T} , while in the exportation orders, the terminal is the destination. Subsets
428 \mathcal{O}^{IE} and \mathcal{O}^{OE} are flexible orders, which represent requests and removals of empty containers. In these orders,
429 only some parameters are known in advance. For example, the origin of a container in a request for an empty
430 container order could be the depot, \dot{D} , or the container removal from an outbound empty container order.

431 Because the problem under study allows soft time windows, some penalization costs have assumed if the
432 orders are not performed within the time window associated:

- 433 • An exportation order cannot begin before the container is ready in the origin (see Figure 3.a). In the
434 destination, the terminal, breaking the time window due to delays means missing the train or ship
435 responsible for the main transportation. Thus, a high penalty cost is generated by missing the main
436 transport, C_i^m . Moreover, dropping the container off early can result in extra storage costs, C_i^s . This
437 is shown in Figure 3.b.
- 438 • In importation orders, the container cannot be retired before this arrives. Moreover, as shown in Figure
439 3.c, breaching the time windows in the origin due to delays means extra storage costs due to the waiting
440 time, C_i^s . The penalization of the destination could be modelled with the origin time windows. Thus,
441 no extra constraints are added (see Figure 3.d).
- 442 • In inbound empty container orders (see Figure 3.b), there exist two penalization costs, one relative to
443 early deliveries and another relative to delayed deliveries.
- 444 • In outbound empty containers, as shown in Figure 3.c, a cost relative to removal delays exists.

445 A fleet of vehicles exists to perform all orders. C_v is the cost of using a new vehicle. Each vehicle has
446 been modelled by means of two dummy orders; thus, different origins, destinations and working times can be
447 considered. One dummy order represents the beginning of the working day, and another represents the end.
448 These orders are included in the sets \mathcal{O}^{VI} and \mathcal{O}^{VE} . The workday is framed in a time window; before the
449 end of the day, all trucks have to return to the vehicle depot, \dot{V} , in the case of noncompliance there exist an
450 extra cost. The penalty will be a cost per unit of time of delay, C_i^d .

Figure 3: Time windows

451 The inclusion of these dummy orders and the soft time windows where some delays are allowed (although
 452 with penalty costs) allows the model to be adapted to dynamic and probabilistic problems in which there
 453 could exist delays in the services and displacement times. Moreover, this lets us use the model in methods
 454 as the rolling horizon. In these cases, it is necessary to know which vehicles have been previously used. This
 455 information is in the parameter U_i (1 if $i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}$ was used, else 0).

456 The variables of the model are:

- 457 • x_{ij} , binary variable. 1 if orders i and j are served consecutively, else 0.
- 458 • n_i , binary variable. 1 if new vehicle i is used, else 0 (in dynamic problems).
- 459 • t_i^o start time of the order i in the origin (load).
- 460 • t_i^d : start time of the order i in the destination (unload)
- 461 • w_i^o Delay time on the later expected beginning time in order i , extra storage cost.
- 462 • w_i^d Advance time at the earliest planned start time in order i , extra storage cost.
- 463 • $w_i^{\dot{V}}$ Delay time of the vehicle i in the latest expected hour of arrival at the depot of vehicles (\dot{V}).
- 464 • l_i^d binary variable. 1 if order i break its destination time window, else 0.

465 To facilitate the modelling, three auxiliary parameters are defined:

- 466 • T_i , which represents the time of loading the container in the origin of order i and the displacement to
 467 the destination of i .
- 468 • T_{ij} , which represents the time of unloading the container in the destination of order i and the displace-
 469 ment to the origin of order j .
- 470 • C_{ij} , which represents the distance of displacement of order i plus the distance between destination of
 471 i and origin of j .

472 The values of these parameters depend on the sequence in which the orders are performed. Supposing a
473 unique terminal (\dot{T}), depot (\dot{D}) of containers and depot of vehicles (\dot{V}), the values of these parameter are
474 as shown in Table 2. The model can be easily extrapolated to problems with several terminals or depots.
475 δ_{AB} represents the distance between two geographical localization, A and B , and τ_{AB} is the expected travel
476 time between those points. For example: $\tau_{\dot{V}o_j}$ is the expected travel time between the vehicle depot and the the
477 origin of the order j and $\delta_{o_i d_i}$ represent the distance between origin and destination of the order i .

Table 2: Transition time and costs

ij	\mathcal{O}^I	\mathcal{O}^E	\mathcal{O}^{IE}	\mathcal{O}^{OE}	\mathcal{O}^{VE}
\mathcal{O}^{VI}	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = \tau_{\dot{V}\dot{T}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{V}\dot{T}}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = \tau_{\dot{V}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{V}o_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = \tau_{\dot{V}\dot{D}} + s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}d_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{V}\dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}d_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = \tau_{\dot{V}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{V}o_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = 0$ $C_{ij} = 0$
\mathcal{O}^I	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{\dot{T}d_i}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i\dot{T}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{T}d_i} + \delta_{d_i\dot{T}}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{\dot{T}d_i}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{T}d_i} + \delta_{d_i o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{\dot{T}d_i}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i \dot{D}} + s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}d_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{T}d_i} + \delta_{d_i \dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}d_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{\dot{T}d_i}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{T}d_i} + \delta_{d_i o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{\dot{T}d_i}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i \dot{V}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{\dot{T}d_i} + \delta_{d_i \dot{V}}$
\mathcal{O}^E	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{T}}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{T}}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{T}}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{\dot{T}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{T}} + \delta_{\dot{T}o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{T}}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{\dot{T}\dot{D}} + s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}d_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{T}} + \delta_{\dot{T}\dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}d_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{T}}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{\dot{T}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \tau_{o_i \dot{T}} + \delta_{\dot{T}o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{T}}$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{\dot{T}\dot{V}}$ $C_{ij} = \tau_{o_i \dot{T}} \tau_{\dot{T}\dot{V}}$
\mathcal{O}^{IE}	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i \dot{T}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i \dot{T}}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i o_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i \dot{D}} + s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}d_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i \dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}d_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i o_j}$	$T_i = 0$ $T_{ij} = s_i^d + \tau_{d_i \dot{V}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i \dot{V}}$
\mathcal{O}^{OE}	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{D}}$ $T_{ij} = s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}\dot{T}}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}\dot{T}}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{D}}$ $T_{ij} = s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o$ $T_{ij} = \tau_{d_i o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{d_i o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{D}}$ $T_{ij} = s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}o_j}$ $C_{ij} = \delta_{o_i \dot{D}} + \delta_{\dot{D}o_j}$	$T_i = s_i^o + \tau_{o_i \dot{D}}$ $T_{ij} = s_{\dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}\dot{V}}$ $C_{ij} = \tau_{o_i \dot{D}} + \tau_{\dot{D}\dot{V}}$

478 Of the information shown in Table 2, it is important to highlight that, in the flexible orders, subsets IE
479 and OE, the containers have the depot (\dot{D}) as origin and destination. However, when an IE order is executed
480 after an OE order, the container is transferred directly (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Savings for merging flexible empty container orders

481 With the above notation, the DDPTW problem is formulated as shown:

$$\begin{aligned}
OF : \min & \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI} \cup \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}} C_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}} C_v n_i + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE}} C_i^s w_i^d \right. \\
& \left. + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^{OE}} C_i^s w_i^o + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE}} C_j^m l_j^d + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^{VE}} C_i^d w_i^{\dot{V}} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI} \cup \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}, \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}, \tag{3}$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI} \cup \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}} x_{ji} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{O}, \tag{4}$$

$$t_i^o \geq E_i^o \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{OE} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{5}$$

$$t_i^d \geq E_i^d \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{6}$$

$$E_i^d - t_i^d \geq w_i^d \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE}, \tag{7}$$

$$t_i^d \geq t_i^o + T_i \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{8}$$

$$t_i^d + T_{ij} - t_j^o \leq M \cdot (1 - x_{ij}) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VI}, \forall j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}, \tag{9}$$

$$t_i^o - L_i^o \leq M \cdot w_i^o \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^{OE}, \tag{10}$$

$$t_j^d - L_j^d \leq M \cdot l_j^d \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE}, \tag{11}$$

$$t_i^o - L_i^o \leq M \cdot w_i^{\dot{V}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VE}, \tag{12}$$

$$\left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} \right) - U_i \leq n_i \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}, \tag{13}$$

$$t_i^o \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{OE} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{14}$$

$$t_i^d \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{15}$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI} \cup \mathcal{O}, j \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{O}^{VE}, \tag{16}$$

$$n_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}, \tag{17}$$

$$w_i^o \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^{OE} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{18}$$

$$w_i^d \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^I \cup \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE} \cup \mathcal{O}^V, \tag{19}$$

$$l_j^d \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{O}^E \cup \mathcal{O}^{IE}, \tag{20}$$

$$w_i^{\dot{V}} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{O}^{VE}, \tag{21}$$

482 The objective function of the model aims to minimize the total amount of costs associated with a solution
483 to the problem: (a) costs associated with the total distance travelled, (b) the fixed costs associated with the
484 number of vehicles required, and (c) the costs generated by the breaches of the time windows.

485 Restrictions are divided into several groups. (2-4) indicate that each task should be covered once. (5-12)
486 represent the restrictions of time windows. As can be observed, this work contemplates soft time windows.
487 M represent a great number. (13) indicate if a new vehicle is used, since the model is adapted to dynamic
488 resolution, U_i indicates if a vehicle $i \in \mathcal{O}^{VI}$ has been previously used. (14-20) define variables in a range,
489 whether as binary (decision variables) or positive (those that record time).

490 The commercial software Gurobi v7.5 was used to solve the formulation shown previously. The default
491 setting of tolerance was modified to make the method more restrictive: the parameter *FeasibilityTol*, which
492 establishes the tolerance of the constraints, was set to 10^{-9} . The MIP solver of Gurobi terminate, considering
493 optimal result, when the gap between the lower and upper objective bound is less than *MIPGap* times the
494 absolute value of the upper bound; so this parameter was set to 0. The maximum time expended was fixed
495 in 3600 seconds.

496 5. Experimental design

497 Despite the number of studies focused on different variants of DDP, it is impossible to develop a clear
498 comparison among them. This is because the different experiments and tests do not follow a common
499 framework. The clusters of researchers have independently developed their own tests, and sometimes these
500 are not published; consequently, these experiments are not replicable.

501 A summary of the different tests and their characteristics is shown in Table 3. This table contains
502 information regarding the origin of the data (artificial or based on a realistic environment), the possibility
503 of replicating the test (y: yes, n: no, m: the experiment could be replicated but the results are not directly
504 comparable), the maximum number of orders, and the characteristics of the time windows. This table also
505 shows which works were developed by the same cluster of researchers.

506 This paper aims to establish a common framework for DDP studies. With this objective, two different
507 batteries of tests are proposed. These batteries are designed to discover the performances of the approach in
508 several environments.

509 The first battery (B1) only has importation and exportation orders, it is to say, the battery only contains
510 well-defined orders. The second battery (B2) also considers movements of empty containers, so both, well-
511 defined and flexible orders are taken into account. This benchmark provides an extensive variety of cases,
512 with several time windows and positions of the customers (See Table 4). The customers can be randomly
513 distributed (R), clustered (C) or a mixed model (RC). There are tests in which all the orders have time
514 windows, while for other tests, only a percentage have this restriction. Moreover, the lengths of the time
515 windows can vary from very narrow windows to much wider windows.

516 Both batteries are developed with different numbers of orders. In B1 28 different tests were completed
517 with 4 problem sizes (10 orders, 25 orders, 50 orders and 100 orders). Since B2 is an extension of some tests
518 of the first one, again four different numbers of orders are tested (20, 50, 100 and 200) for 21 different test.
519 So, a total of 196 tests were studied.

Table 3: Summary of test batteries in the drayage literature

Cluster	Paper	Artificial	Base Real	Replicable	n. orders	TW characteristic (min)
	Wang and Regan (2002)	x		n	Up to 150	30, 90, 240
A	Cheung and Hang (2003)	x		n	Up to 50	U[120,360]
A	Cheung et al. (2005)	x		n	Up to 200	U[120,360]
	Ileri et al. (2006)		x	n	Up to 60	n.i.
B	Jula et al. (2005)	x	x	n	Up to 100	30, 60, 120, 180 min
B	Coslovich et al. (2006)	x	x	n	Up to 359	n.i.
B	Jula et al. (2006)		x	n	Up to 4208	--
C	Smilowitz (2006)	x	x	n	Up to 621	n.i.
C	Francis et al. (2007)	x		n	Up to 100	n.i.
C	Zhang et al. (2011a)	x		n	Up to 75	120 -720
	Imai et al. (2007)	x		n	Up to 200	--
	Chung et al. (2007)		x	y	700 aprox.	--
D	Caris and Janssens (2009)	x		m	Up to 200	U[60,120] or U[90,240]
D	Caris and Janssens (2010)			m	Up to 200	U[60,120]
D	Braekers et al. (2013)	x		m	Up to 200	U[60,120] or U[120,240]
D	Braekers et al. (2014)	x		m	Up to 200	U[60,120] or U[120,240]
E	Escudero et al. (2009)	x		m	Up to 100	U[30,240]
E	Escudero et al. (2011a)	x		m	Up to 100	U[60,120] or U[90,240]
E	Escudero et al. (2011b)	x		y	Up to 100	(*)
E	Escudero et al. (2013)	x		y	Up to 100	(*)
E	Escudero et al. (2015)	x		y	Up to 100	(*)
F	Zhang et al. (2009)	x		n	Up to 200	U[0,180]
F	Zhang et al. (2010)	x		n	Up to 75	60, 120, 180, 240
F	Zhang et al. (2011b)	x		n	Up to 75	U[0,240] in O U[0,300] in D
F	Sterzik and Kopfer (2013)	x		n	Up to 75	(*)(+)
F	Wang and Yun (2013)	x		n	Up to 40	U[0,180]
F	Zhang et al. (2014)	x		n	Up to 66	0 - 120
F	Sterzik et al. (2015)	x		n	Up to 75	(+)
F	Zhang et al. (2015)	x		n	Up to 75	--
F	Funke and Kopfer (2016)	x		n	(#)	(#)
	Mahr et al. (2010)		x	n	Up to 65	120
	Lai et al. (2013)	x	x	n	Up to 250	--
	Nossack and Pesch (2013)	x		n	Up to 75	(+) or 600, 660, 720
	Pazour and Neubert (2013)		x	n	n.i.	--
	Sun et al. (2014)	x	x	n	Up to 450	n.i.
G	Xue et al. (2014)		x	n	Up to 200	U[180,300]
G	Xue et al. (2015)		x	n	Up to 200	U[180,300]
	Bai et al. (2015)	x	x	y	Up to 2000	60 - 4320 min
	Caballini et al. (2016)		x	n	Up to 220	600 or 900 min
	Reinhant et al. (2016)	x	x	n	Up to 308	n.i.
	Shiri and Huynh (2016)	x		n	Up to 200	240
	Song et al. (2016)	x		n	Up to 35	240
	Vidovic et al. (2016)	x		y	Up to 100	(*)
	Daham et al. (2017)	x		n	Up to 350	n.i.
	Ritzinger et al. (2017)	x		n	Up to 50	30

NOTES: In Chung et al. (2007) Bai et al. (2015) the orders are performed among terminals (max. 10 nodes)
 (*) Based on Solomon (1987) (+) Based on Zhang et al. (2010) (#) Based on Sterzik and Kopfer (2013)

Table 4: Characteristics of the tests in batteries

Battery	Class	Test	Orders	Customers	TW	Length TW	Problem Sizes
B1	B1_R	1	I, E	Random (R)	100%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	2	I, E	Random (R)	75%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	3	I, E	Random (R)	50%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	4	I, E	Random (R)	25%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	5	I, E	Random (R)	100%	90	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	6	I, E	Random (R)	100%	120	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	7	I, E	Random (R)	100%	240	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	8	I, E	Random (R)	100%	120*	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	9	I, E	Random (R)	100%	240*	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_R	10	I, E	Random (R)	100%	30	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	1	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	2	I, E	Cluster (C)	75%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	3	I, E	Cluster (C)	50%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	4	I, E	Cluster (C)	25%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	5	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	90	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	6	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	120	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	7	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	240	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	8	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	120*	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_C	9	I, E	Cluster (C)	100%	240*	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	1	I, E	RC	100%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	2	I, E	RC	75%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	3	I, E	RC	50%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	4	I, E	RC	25%	60	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	5	I, E	RC	100%	90	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	6	I, E	RC	100%	120	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	7	I, E	RC	100%	240	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	8	I, E	RC	100%	120*	10, 25, 50, 100
B1	B1_RC	9	I, E	RC	100%	240*	10, 25, 50, 100
B2	B2_R	1	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	30	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	2	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	60	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	3	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	90	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	4	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	120	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	5	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	240	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	6	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	120*	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_R	7	I, E, IE, OE	Random (R)	100%	240*	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	1	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	30	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	2	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	60	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	3	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	90	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	4	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	120	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	5	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	240	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	6	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	120*	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_C	7	I, E, IE, OE	Cluster (C)	100%	240*	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	1	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	30	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	2	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	60	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	3	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	90	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	4	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	120	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	5	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	240	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	6	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	120*	20, 50, 100, 200
B2	B2_RC	7	I, E, IE, OE	RC	100%	240*	20, 50, 100, 200
(120*) There exist fixed slot a long the day [[0-120][120-240][240-360][360-480][480-600][600-720]]							
(240*) There exist fixed slot a long the day [[0-240][240-480][480-720]]							

520 This wide variety allows the different stakeholders to learn the impact of their decisions on adequate
521 planning of the movements. For example, in the case of route planners, this common benchmark would
522 let them determine which method of resolution is most appropriate depending on the characteristics of the
523 terminal in which they are developed. In the case of terminal managers, it will allow them to discover the
524 effects of different policies, for example, by imposing very limited access appointments.

525 The designed benchmark is published at a provided URL. Without loss of generality, the terminal lo-
526 calization, the vehicle depot and the container depot have the same localization. Other parameters of the
527 benchmarks are not fixed in the URL. However, in most of the experiments, these parameters are equal. The
528 mean speed is 60 km/h, the time of loading and unloading is 15 min, the cost per kilometre is 1, the waiting
529 cost is 10 per hour, and the cost of failing to complete a task is 1000. The fixed cost per vehicle is 10 or 100.

530 **6. Results**

531 Using the proposed benchmark, different studies were developed. First, we tested the performance of
532 the method considering hard time windows, so we run both batteries. Tables show the achieved results,
533 including the minimum cost found, the distance and number of vehicles of the solution, the gap between the
534 lower bound and the solution, and the execution time. Since convergence of exact methods is not guaranteed
535 within a reasonable time, the execution of each problem was limited to one hour.

536 The achieved results on B1, test battery with only exportation and importation orders, are presented
537 in Table 5. Two cases of fixed cost per vehicle are studied: 10 and 100. These two cases let us analyze
538 two different sceneries: companies with wide fleets of vehicles (and with permanent resources to execute the
539 orders) and companies that need to subcontract drivers or even the complete execution of some orders. The
540 comparison of the two cases shows that an increase in fixed cost per vehicle usually leads to a reduction in
541 the fleet required, but an increase in the total distance travelled. In other words, reduced fleets will lead
542 to an increase in the distance travelled when trying to make profitable use of existing resources. As it has
543 been widely studied in this field, this study confirms that collaboration and cooperation among companies
544 significantly reduces the distance travelled, which would also lead to environmental benefits.

545 Moreover, since this battery contains tests with the same orders but different lengths of time windows we
546 can explore the influence of time windows restriction over the cost of the solution. By analysing the results of
547 these tests, we can state that the increase in time windows represents savings of operating costs (see Figure
548 5). In realistic environments, with a number of orders to be carried out between 25 and 100, doubling the
549 duration of the time window implies reductions in transport costs of around 6-7%. Besides, we can achieve
550 identical conclusion when not all the orders have time window restriction (See Figure 6). Analyzing this
551 image, some significant results can be observed. Allowing some customers total flexibility in their port access
552 results in cost savings. When this flexibility affects 25% of the orders, a cost saving of around 10% is achieved.
553 This saving increases as the number of orders involved increases, although the increase is not so significant.
554 In scenarios with 75% truck without port access restrictions the saving is around 15%.

Table 5: Result of the problem class B1 (hard time windows)

N. Orders	CLASS	TEST	TW	Vehicle Cost = 10					Vehicle Cost = 100					Δ Veh.	Δ Dist.	
				N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time	N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time			
10	B1_R	1	30	3	388.15	418.15	0.00%	0.01	2	420.58	620.58	0.00%	0.00	0.00	-1.00	32.43
	B1_R	2	60	3	388.15	418.15	0.00%	0.04	2	399.02	599.02	0.00%	0.07	-1.00	10.87	
	B1_R	3	60	2	369.95	389.95	0.00%	0.02	2	369.95	569.95	0.00%	0.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	4	60	2	357.42	377.42	0.00%	0.01	2	357.42	557.42	0.00%	0.04	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	5	60	1	335.09	345.09	0.00%	0.16	1	335.09	435.09	0.00%	0.05	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	6	90	2	388.15	408.15	0.00%	0.01	2	388.15	588.15	0.00%	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	7	120	2	388.15	408.15	0.00%	0.02	2	388.15	588.15	0.00%	0.07	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	8	240	2	357.42	377.42	0.00%	0.05	1	370.35	470.35	0.00%	0.07	-1.00	12.93	
	B1_R	9	120*	2	402.21	422.21	0.00%	0.01	2	402.21	602.21	0.00%	0.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	10	240*	1	379.78	389.78	0.00%	0.01	1	379.78	479.78	0.00%	0.05	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	1	60	3	260.97	290.97	0.00%	0.05	2	290.90	490.90	0.00%	0.00	-1.00	29.93	
	B1_C	2	60	2	228.87	248.87	0.00%	0.10	2	228.87	428.87	0.00%	0.06	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	3	60	2	197.95	217.95	0.00%	0.06	2	197.95	397.95	0.00%	0.06	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	4	60	1	197.95	207.95	0.00%	0.05	1	197.95	297.95	0.00%	0.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	5	90	2	260.97	280.97	0.00%	0.00	2	260.97	460.97	0.00%	0.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	6	120	1	265.55	275.55	0.00%	0.01	1	265.55	365.55	0.00%	0.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	7	240	1	198.58	208.58	0.00%	0.04	1	198.58	298.58	0.00%	0.09	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	8	120*	2	293.19	313.19	0.00%	0.00	2	293.19	493.19	0.00%	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	9	240*	1	291.34	301.34	0.00%	0.09	1	291.34	391.34	0.00%	0.08	0.00	0.00	
	B1_RC	1	60	3	517.44	547.44	0.00%	0.06	3	517.44	817.44	0.00%	0.06	0.00	0.00	
B1_RC	2	60	3	448.79	478.79	0.00%	0.05	2	496.70	696.70	0.00%	0.14	-1.00	47.90		
B1_RC	3	60	2	439.59	459.59	0.00%	0.04	2	439.59	639.59	0.00%	0.05	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	4	60	2	439.59	459.59	0.00%	0.03	2	439.59	639.59	0.00%	0.04	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	5	90	3	517.44	547.44	0.00%	0.01	2	577.60	777.60	0.00%	0.01	-1.00	60.16		
B1_RC	6	120	2	517.44	537.44	0.00%	0.01	2	517.44	717.44	0.00%	0.01	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	7	240	2	511.30	531.30	0.00%	0.07	2	511.30	711.30	0.00%	0.40	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	8	120*	2	654.80	674.80	0.00%	0.01	2	654.80	854.80	0.00%	0.00	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	9	240*	2	584.69	604.69	0.00%	0.03	2	584.69	784.69	0.00%	0.05	0.00	0.00		
25	B1_R	1	30	7	1013.22	1083.22	0.00%	0.02	6	1036.18	1636.18	0.00%	0.02	-1.00	22.96	
	B1_R	2	60	4	1029.03	1069.03	0.00%	0.05	4	1029.03	1429.03	0.00%	0.19	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	3	60	4	898.77	938.77	0.00%	0.78	3	922.07	1222.07	0.00%	41.27	-1.00	23.30	
	B1_R	4	60	3	871.69	901.69	0.00%	10.04	3	871.69	1171.69	6.90%	3600.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	5	60	3	823.09	853.09	1.77%	3600.02	3	823.09	1123.09	17.7%	3600.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	6	90	4	963.22	1003.22	0.00%	0.07	3	977.91	1277.91	0.00%	1.19	-1.00	16.68	
	B1_R	7	120	4	940.74	980.74	0.00%	0.10	3	970.92	1270.92	0.00%	1.20	-1.00	30.18	
	B1_R	8	240	3	851.80	881.80	0.00%	1.93	3	851.80	1151.80	5.49%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	9	120*	4	917.07	957.07	0.00%	0.19	3	949.56	1249.56	0.00%	0.95	-1.00	32.49	
	B1_R	10	240*	4	855.72	895.72	0.00%	3.96	3	870.65	1170.65	0.00%	2023.56	-1.00	14.93	
	B1_C	1	60	4	751.02	791.02	0.00%	0.05	4	751.02	1151.02	0.00%	0.15	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	2	60	4	681.96	721.96	0.00%	0.83	3	711.16	1011.16	0.00%	122.56	-1.00	29.21	
	B1_C	3	60	3	644.54	674.54	0.00%	27.65	3	644.54	944.54	9.40%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	4	60	2	629.02	649.02	1.36%	3600.01	2	629.02	829.02	12.06%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	5	90	4	731.02	771.02	0.00%	0.17	3	746.16	1046.16	0.00%	0.36	-1.00	15.14	
	B1_C	6	120	3	715.24	745.24	0.00%	0.29	3	715.24	1015.24	0.00%	6.41	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	7	240	3	634.82	664.82	0.00%	3.61	3	634.82	934.82	14.06%	3600.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	8	120*	3	739.81	769.81	0.00%	0.17	3	739.81	1039.81	0.00%	2.44	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	9	240*	3	708.77	738.77	0.00%	1899.95	3	708.77	1008.77	16.26%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_RC	1	60	4	1364.54	1404.54	0.00%	0.03	4	1364.54	1764.54	0.00%	0.07	0.00	0.00	
B1_RC	2	60	4	1150.56	1190.56	0.00%	0.40	4	1150.56	1550.56	0.00%	10.88	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	3	60	3	1143.70	1173.70	0.00%	11.60	3	1143.70	1443.70	0.00%	102.78	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	4	60	3	1138.48	1168.48	0.83%	3600.01	3	1138.48	1438.48	6.95%	3600.02	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	5	90	4	1340.92	1380.92	0.00%	0.03	4	1340.92	1740.92	0.00%	0.30	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	6	120	4	1240.89	1280.89	0.00%	0.11	4	1240.89	1640.89	0.00%	1.24	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	7	240	3	1223.47	1253.47	0.00%	14.33	3	1223.47	1523.47	0.00%	251.83	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	8	120*	4	1407.48	1447.48	0.00%	0.15	4	1407.48	1807.48	0.00%	0.92	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC	9	240*	4	1301.77	1341.77	0.00%	157.96	3	1333.96	1633.96	1.87%	3600.01	-1.00	32.20		
50	B1_R	1	30	11	1973.38	2083.38	0.00%	0.12	9	2004.99	2904.99	0.00%	0.10	-2.00	31.61	
	B1_R	2	60	9	1949.14	2039.14	0.00%	0.56	7	2003.75	2703.75	0.00%	1.15	-2.00	54.61	
	B1_R	3	60	7	1824.99	1894.99	0.00%	37.48	6	1877.69	2477.69	10.85%	3600.01	-1.00	52.69	
	B1_R	4	60	5	1776.30	1826.30	0.47%	3600.02	5	1789.99	2289.99	8.17%	3600.01	0.00	13.69	
	B1_R	5	60	5	1703.98	1753.98	1.71%	3600.01	5	1703.98	2203.98	16.99%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	6	90	7	1931.55	2001.55	0.00%	1.54	6	1974.49	2574.49	0.00%	25.30	-1.00	42.94	
	B1_R	7	120	6	1843.86	1903.86	0.00%	4.34	6	1843.86	2443.86	3.87%	3600.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_R	8	240	5	1722.40	1772.40	1.59%	3600.01	5	1725.24	2225.24	21.42%	3600.02	0.00	2.84	
	B1_R	9	120*	7	1837.63	1907.63	0.00%	0.39	5	1893.55	2393.55	1.00%	3600.03	-2.00	55.92	
	B1_R	10	240*	6	1758.18	1818.18	1.07%	3600.01	6	1758.18	2358.18	19.18%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	1	60	9	1553.61	1643.61	0.00%	0.20	7	1602.19	2302.19	0.00%	1.93	-2.00	48.58	
	B1_C	2	60	7	1433.12	1503.12	0.00%	33.30	6	1449.01	2049.01	8.14%	3600.02	-1.00	15.88	
	B1_C	3	60	5	1371.06	1421.06	0.00%	137.86	5	1371.06	1871.06	4.99%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	4	60	5	1366.50	1416.50	2.12%	3600.01	5	1366.50	1866.50	16.07%	3600.03	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	5	90	7	1505.26	1575.26	0.00%	0.78	6	1541.26	2141.26	0.00%	122.78	-1.00	35.99	
	B1_C	6	120	6	1490.08	1550.08	0.00%	4.99	5	1570.41	2070.41	6.93%	3600.03	-1.00	80.33	
	B1_C	7	240	5	1389.35	1439.35	1.39%	3600.01	5	1389.35	1889.35	24.12%	3600.01	0.00	0.00	
	B1_C	8	120*	6	1509.58	1569.58	0.00%	0.53	5	1534.62	2034.62	0.00%	1189.95	-1.00	25.04	
	B1_C	9	240*	5	1466.54	1516.54	0.34%	3600.02	5	1466.54	1966.54	14.23%	3600.02	0.00	0.00	
	B1_RC	1	60	9	2833.03	2923.03	0.00%	0.40	9	2833.03	3733.03	0.00%	1.21	0.00	0.00	
B1_RC	2	60	8	2565.72	2645.72	0.00%	3.09	8	2565.72	3365.72	0.00%	1730.79	0.00	0.00		
B1_RC																

Figure 5: Effect of the increase the time windows.

Figure 6: Effect of reducing orders with time window restriction

555 Another important analyses is to know the effect of allowing flexible orders in the performance of inbound
556 and outbound empty container orders. Table 6 shows the results of the B2 considering a fixed cost per vehicle
557 equal to 10. Two cases are considered regarding the empty container movements: (a) well-defined orders, so
558 the reposition of empty container must be done by means of the depot, and (b) flexible orders. By analysing
559 the results of the B2, it is clear that this flexibility involves cost savings for the operations.

560 All the policy studies seen above, which have been numerically justified, are in line with the logical
561 assumption that more flexibility enables more cost-effective solutions. In the case of flexibility in the reposi-
562 tioning of empty containers, this flexibility means an overall benefit for all actors: cost reduction, possibility
563 of attending to a greater number of tasks, reduction in the number of operations needed in the depot, etc.
564 This would reduce traffic congestion in a high-traffic area. If the depot were located near the terminal, this
565 benefit would be even more significant.

566 Flexibility in time windows, considering it either the absence of restriction or a sufficiently large time
567 window, would help reduce the costs of the haulage operations, but it would make the management of the
568 port operations more difficult. It is becoming increasingly common for ports to try to impose a series of
569 temporary slots for the transit of trucks in and out of the port. This way, both unnecessary congestion events
570 at the gates and trucks waiting to be handled are avoided. In essence, knowing in advance the arrival time
571 of the trucks let the terminal improve its management and size its resources properly.

572 Therefore, there are conflicting interests between two actors in the intermodal chain: the terminal man-
573 agers and the haulage operators. This work studies the effect of flexible time windows, where those trans-
574 porters who adapt to the agreed window are rewarded, but a certain flexibility is provided to cover the regular
575 incidents and uncertainties in this type of operation.

576 Finally, the effects of soft time windows versus strict time windows were studied. In the case of DDP, we
577 only consider soft time windows when the missing the main transport in the terminal is not considered. In
578 Table 7, the results of the method in both cases are compared. We can observe the savings that the flexibility
579 in the completion of the orders suppose due to the soft time windows. In Figure 7 the costs of the operative
580 with strict time windows (120 and 240 minutes) are compared to the costs of the operative with soft time
581 windows (30, 60 and 90 minutes), different waiting cost per hour are analysed. Below a certain waiting cost,
582 it is possible to achieve costs in the operation with narrow time windows at the level of those with wider
583 time windows.

584 Such a policy would help plan operations within terminals more efficiently by greatly reducing the uncer-
585 tainty in arrivals without prejudicing the costs involved for the transport company.

586 7. Conclusion

587 This paper intends to achieve three objectives. First, we have carried out a thorough bibliographic study
588 of the works presented to date in relation to drayage operations, especially those that present quantitative
589 models. The number of papers published in this field has increased in recent years. This is undoubtedly due

Table 6: Result of the problem class B2 (hard time windows)

N. Orders	CLASS	TEST	TW	Well-defined Orders					Flexible Orders					Improve
				N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time	N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time	
20	B2_R	1	30	5	557,87	607,87	0,00%	0,09	5	540,85	590,85	0,00%	0,10	2,88%
	B2_R	2	60	5	557,87	607,87	0,00%	0,02	5	540,85	590,85	0,00%	0,02	2,88%
	B2_R	3	90	4	513,15	553,15	0,00%	0,05	4	496,13	536,13	0,00%	0,03	3,17%
	B2_R	4	120	3	477,15	507,15	0,00%	0,04	3	440,25	470,25	0,00%	0,05	7,85%
	B2_R	5	240	2	601,65	621,65	0,00%	0,55	2	403,08	423,08	0,00%	0,60	46,93%
	B2_R	6	120*	2	434,72	454,72	0,00%	0,03	2	402,21	422,21	0,00%	0,04	7,70%
	B2_R	7	240*	2	434,72	454,72	0,00%	0,16	2	379,78	399,78	0,00%	0,10	13,74%
	B2_C	1	30	6	399,02	459,02	0,00%	0,01	6	365,28	425,28	0,00%	0,10	7,93%
	B2_C	2	60	5	389,53	439,53	0,00%	0,02	5	355,79	405,79	0,00%	0,02	8,31%
	B2_C	3	90	4	357,28	397,28	0,00%	0,02	3	295,17	325,17	0,00%	0,04	22,17%
	B2_C	4	120	3	357,28	387,28	0,00%	0,02	3	295,17	325,17	0,00%	0,06	19,10%
	B2_C	5	240	2	357,28	377,28	0,00%	2,72	2	260,97	280,97	0,00%	0,47	34,28%
	B2_C	6	120*	2	357,28	377,28	0,00%	0,04	2	325,41	345,41	0,00%	0,09	9,22%
	B2_C	7	240*	2	357,28	377,28	0,00%	0,29	2	291,34	311,34	0,00%	0,43	21,18%
	B2_RC	1	30	7	863,49	933,49	0,00%	0,02	7	863,49	933,49	0,00%	0,02	0,00%
	B2_RC	2	60	6	776,57	836,57	0,00%	0,03	6	776,57	836,57	0,00%	0,02	0,00%
	B2_RC	3	90	5	776,57	826,57	0,00%	0,02	4	753,07	793,07	0,00%	0,02	4,22%
	B2_RC	4	120	3	728,96	758,96	0,00%	0,02	4	668,80	708,80	0,00%	0,03	7,08%
	B2_RC	5	240	2	714,96	734,96	0,00%	0,28	3	517,44	547,44	0,00%	0,08	34,26%
	B2_RC	6	120*	4	862,19	902,19	0,00%	0,02	4	744,24	784,24	0,00%	0,03	15,04%
	B2_RC	7	240*	3	714,96	744,96	0,00%	0,23	3	584,69	614,69	0,00%	0,34	21,19%
50	B2_R	1	30	9	1381,05	1471,05	0,00%	0,07	9	1244,59	1334,59	0,00%	0,07	10,22%
	B2_R	2	60	7	1381,05	1451,05	0,00%	0,10	7	1254,45	1324,45	0,00%	0,10	9,56%
	B2_R	3	90	5	1309,47	1359,47	0,00%	0,11	6	1173,01	1233,01	0,00%	0,13	10,26%
	B2_R	4	120	5	1288,59	1338,59	0,00%	0,60	6	1089,55	1149,55	0,00%	0,16	16,44%
	B2_R	5	240	5	1599,20	1649,20	0,00%	1711,19	5	951,30	1001,30	0,00%	3042,35	64,71%
	B2_R	6	120*	6	1246,16	1306,16	0,00%	1,11	6	1024,17	1084,17	0,00%	0,61	20,48%
	B2_R	7	240*	5	1246,16	1296,16	2,31%	3600,01	5	855,72	905,72	0,00%	3,44	43,11%
	B2_C	1	30	9	1173,94	1263,94	0,00%	0,07	9	964,94	1054,94	0,00%	0,20	19,81%
	B2_C	2	60	7	1164,45	1234,45	0,00%	0,09	7	955,45	1025,45	0,00%	0,32	20,38%
	B2_C	3	90	7	1132,20	1202,20	0,00%	0,09	6	889,01	949,01	0,00%	0,10	26,68%
	B2_C	4	120	5	1132,20	1182,20	0,00%	0,13	5	876,62	926,62	0,00%	0,23	27,58%
	B2_C	5	240	4	1132,20	1172,20	1,35%	3600,01	4	807,99	847,99	0,00%	4,31	38,23%
	B2_C	6	120*	6	1132,20	1192,20	0,00%	5,04	6	792,65	852,65	0,00%	21,51	39,82%
	B2_C	7	240*	5	1132,20	1182,20	2,54%	3600,01	4	714,89	754,89	0,00%	2374,46	56,60%
	B2_RC	1	30	11	2035,19	2145,19	0,00%	0,18	10	1802,75	1902,75	0,00%	0,16	12,74%
	B2_RC	2	60	10	1948,27	2048,27	0,00%	0,11	9	1715,83	1805,83	0,00%	0,08	13,43%
	B2_RC	3	90	7	1948,27	2018,27	0,00%	0,07	7	1692,33	1762,33	0,00%	0,07	14,52%
	B2_RC	4	120	7	1900,66	1970,66	0,00%	0,31	6	1638,26	1698,26	0,00%	0,15	16,04%
	B2_RC	5	240	5	1886,66	1936,66	0,52%	3600,03	5	1403,05	1453,05	0,00%	2,23	33,28%
	B2_RC	6	120*	7	2039,69	2109,69	0,00%	1,19	7	1563,04	1633,04	0,00%	1,99	29,19%
	B2_RC	7	240*	6	1886,66	1946,66	0,51%	3600,04	6	1303,40	1363,40	0,00%	101,24	42,78%
100	B2_R	1	30	18	2884,50	3064,50	0,00%	1,26	19	2527,57	2717,57	0,00%	1,38	12,77%
	B2_R	2	60	16	2769,64	2929,64	0,00%	0,38	16	2412,70	2572,70	0,00%	0,38	13,87%
	B2_R	3	90	12	2688,06	2808,06	0,00%	0,56	12	2262,39	2382,39	0,00%	0,46	17,87%
	B2_R	4	120	10	2651,46	2751,46	0,00%	1,86	11	2169,00	2279,00	0,00%	1,32	20,73%
	B2_R	5	240	11	2998,58	3108,58	3,21%	3600,04	10	1946,92	2046,92	7,98%	3600,03	51,87%
	B2_R	6	120*	10	2707,55	2807,55	0,00%	118,97	12	1967,26	2087,26	0,00%	8,91	34,51%
	B2_R	7	240*	10	2624,75	2724,75	3,11%	3600,04	10	1758,18	1858,18	2,54%	3600,09	46,64%
	B2_C	1	30	19	2538,14	2728,14	0,00%	0,32	19	2023,98	2213,98	0,00%	0,39	23,22%
	B2_C	2	60	16	2528,65	2688,65	0,00%	1,30	16	2014,49	2174,49	0,00%	1,49	23,65%
	B2_C	3	90	13	2487,62	2617,62	0,00%	1,45	12	1963,07	2083,07	0,00%	2,77	25,66%
	B2_C	4	120	10	2453,89	2553,89	0,00%	3,80	11	1888,66	1998,66	0,00%	1,06	27,78%
	B2_C	5	240	9	2411,46	2501,46	2,98%	3600,04	8	1590,92	1670,92	1,07%	3600,05	49,71%
	B2_C	6	120*	9	2482,31	2572,31	0,00%	1086,98	12	1646,78	1766,78	0,57%	3600,06	45,59%
	B2_C	7	240*	10	2411,46	2511,46	3,98%	3600,06	9	1466,54	1556,54	2,65%	3600,10	61,35%
	B2_RC	1	30	22	4472,16	4692,16	0,00%	1,02	21	3937,57	4147,57	0,00%	1,84	13,13%
	B2_RC	2	60	18	4275,30	4455,30	0,00%	0,65	18	3740,70	3920,70	0,00%	0,63	13,64%
	B2_RC	3	90	15	4275,30	4425,30	0,00%	3,33	15	3653,63	3803,63	0,00%	2,91	16,34%
	B2_RC	4	120	13	4077,84	4207,84	0,00%	9,27	13	3429,33	3559,33	0,00%	3,02	18,22%
	B2_RC	5	240	11	4059,84	4169,84	1,68%	3600,03	11	2958,61	3068,61	0,54%	3600,19	35,89%
	B2_RC	6	120*	13	4380,94	4510,94	0,00%	573,95	14	3206,66	3346,66	0,00%	1804,43	34,79%
	B2_RC	7	240*	12	4059,84	4179,84	2,41%	3600,05	12	2625,96	2745,96	5,86%	3600,05	52,22%
200	B2_R	1	30	29	5261,51	5551,51	0,00%	6,53	29	4493,55	4783,55	0,00%	6,49	16,05%
	B2_R	2	60	26	5124,31	5384,31	0,00%	3,67	26	4351,46	4611,46	0,00%	5,44	16,76%
	B2_R	3	90	22	5069,41	5289,41	0,00%	4,26	22	4231,25	4451,25	0,00%	4,49	18,83%
	B2_R	4	120	19	5048,93	5238,93	0,00%	2,67	18	4116,51	4296,51	0,00%	45,07	21,93%
	B2_R	5	240	19	5427,29	5617,29	3,50%	3600,08	19	4011,16	4201,16	17,43%	3600,10	33,71%
	B2_R	6	120*	18	5153,07	5333,07	1,45%	3600,05	21	3810,58	4020,58	3,56%	3600,13	32,64%
	B2_R	7	240*	17	4989,42	5159,42	3,29%	3600,06	18	3271,36	3451,36	3,67%	3600,28	49,49%
	B2_C	1	30	32	6120,45	6440,45	0,00%	2,69	32	5045,63	5365,63	0,00%	12,83	20,03%
	B2_C	2	60	28	5917,91	6197,91	0,00%	5,46	28	4843,09	5123,09	0,00%	6,03	20,98%
	B2_C	3	90	23	5847,12	6077,12	0,00%	12,81	23	4734,20	4964,20	0,00%	31,69	22,42%
	B2_C	4	120	18	5813,39	5993,39	0,00%	24,71	19	4611,39	4801,39	0,00%	67,05	24,83%
	B2_C	5	240	20	5770,96	5970,96	3,04%	3600,09	18	4402,39	4582,39	9,93%	3600,20	30,30%
	B2_C	6	120*	20	5988,85	6188,85	1,69%	3600,05	23	4272,59	4502,59	4,17%	3600,11	37,45%
	B2_C	7	240*	19	5770,96	5960,96	3,10%	3600,08	17	3706,18	3876,18	6,61%	3600,07	53,78%
	B2_RC	1	30	33	7048,88	7378,88	0,00%	9,31	32	5991,28	6311,28	0,00%	8,35	16,92%
	B2_RC	2	60	29	6872,30	7162,30	0,00%	2,03	29	5814,70	6104,70	0,00%	4,96	17,32%
	B2_RC	3	90	25	6880,78	7130,78	0,00%	194,86	25	5717,23	5967,23	0,00%	23,92	19,50%
	B2_RC	4	120	21	6631,54	6841,54	0,00%	15,85	21	5437,12	5647,12	0,00%	100,68	21,15%
	B2_RC	5	240	21	6617,54	6827,54	2,83%	3600,06	19	4785,18	4975,18	2,91%	3600,09	37,23%
	B2_RC	6	120*	21	6960,22	7170,22	1,16%	3600,03	23	5073,94	5303,94	3,88%	3600,07	35,19%
	B2_RC	7	240*	20	6617,54	6817,54	2,79%	3600,06	19	4540,61	4730,61	11,99%	3600,09	44,12%

Table 7: Effects of soft time windows

N. Orders	CLASS	TEST	TW	Hard Time Windows					Soft Time Windows					
				N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time	N. Vehicles	Distance	Cost	GAP	Time	Improve
20	B2_R	1	30	4	582,65	982,65	0,00%	0,11	2	684,85	800,06	0,00%	2,49	22,82%
	B2_R	2	60	4	582,08	982,08	0,00%	0,12	2	597,71	738,34	0,00%	1,27	33,01%
	B2_R	3	90	3	539,23	839,23	0,00%	0,18	2	614,72	681,57	0,00%	2,01	23,13%
	B2_R	4	120	3	440,25	740,25	0,00%	0,47	2	577,83	614,69	0,00%	2,02	20,43%
	B2_R	5	240	2	403,08	603,08	0,00%	652,33	2	388,15	590,36	4,17%	3600,01	2,16%
	B2_C	1	30	3	475,42	775,42	0,00%	0,19	3	637,52	712,50	0,00%	0,69	8,83%
	B2_C	2	60	3	425,85	725,85	0,00%	0,10	2	509,54	568,44	0,00%	0,47	27,69%
	B2_C	3	90	2	350,00	550,00	0,00%	0,08	2	475,17	505,86	0,00%	0,40	8,73%
	B2_C	4	120	2	333,23	533,23	0,00%	0,38	2	475,17	498,05	0,00%	3,01	7,06%
	B2_C	5	240	2	260,97	460,97	0,00%	446,08	2	260,97	460,97	12,81%	3600,01	0,00%
	B2_RC	1	30	5	1007,20	1507,20	0,00%	0,10	2	966,57	1096,00	0,00%	2,52	37,52%
	B2_RC	2	60	5	857,78	1357,78	0,00%	0,02	2	966,57	1074,81	0,00%	1,62	26,33%
	B2_RC	3	90	4	753,07	1153,07	0,00%	0,06	2	871,46	984,21	0,00%	2,30	17,16%
	B2_RC	4	120	3	728,96	1028,96	0,00%	0,19	2	834,80	888,56	0,00%	1,39	15,80%
	B2_RC	5	240	2	541,85	741,85	0,00%	1,01	2	541,85	741,85	0,00%	14,74	0,00%
50	B2_R	1	30	7	1355,03	2055,03	0,00%	0,07	5	1656,71	1769,23	2,86%	3600,02	16,15%
	B2_R	2	60	6	1291,04	1891,04	0,00%	0,11	5	1569,56	1689,95	2,49%	3600,01	11,90%
	B2_R	3	90	5	1204,85	1704,85	0,00%	0,80	4	1479,56	1592,45	3,73%	3600,02	7,06%
	B2_R	4	120	5	1100,24	1600,24	0,00%	16,31	4	1414,48	1508,96	5,24%	3600,01	6,05%
	B2_R	5	240	4	996,92	1396,92	30,26%	3600,02	4	936,76	1368,13	31,66%	3600,02	2,10%
	B2_C	1	30	7	1074,87	1774,87	0,00%	0,33	5	1414,43	1575,29	7,82%	3600,01	12,67%
	B2_C	2	60	6	997,09	1597,09	0,00%	1,12	5	1373,20	1478,06	5,72%	3600,01	8,05%
	B2_C	3	90	5	931,79	1431,79	0,00%	1,67	4	1277,13	1384,09	7,56%	3600,02	3,45%
	B2_C	4	120	5	876,62	1376,62	0,00%	25,86	4	1243,39	1315,00	7,54%	3600,03	4,69%
	B2_C	5	240	4	807,99	1207,99	23,84%	3600,04	5	807,99	1207,99	31,41%	3600,02	0,00%
	B2_RC	1	30	8	1946,46	2746,46	0,00%	0,16	6	2255,83	2402,39	3,77%	3600,02	14,32%
	B2_RC	2	60	7	1887,15	2587,15	0,00%	0,17	5	2179,98	2356,87	2,06%	3600,01	9,77%
	B2_RC	3	90	7	1692,33	2392,33	0,00%	0,57	6	2170,72	2256,06	4,70%	3600,04	6,04%
	B2_RC	4	120	6	1638,26	2238,26	0,00%	0,64	5	2077,72	2160,33	5,39%	3600,01	3,61%
	B2_RC	5	240	5	1403,05	1903,05	6,97%	3600,02	5	1403,05	1903,05	22,44%	3600,03	0,00%

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Effect of the variation in waiting costs

590 to the importance that this part of the intermodal chain has for the viability of the entire chain. We consider
591 that this increased attention from the scientific community requires a study to analyse the research trends
592 in this field. To this end, in addition to the description of all the references analysed, a compilation of the
593 works has been shown, presented via a table that summarizes the main characteristics of every paper.

594 The second objective addresses a gap detected in the literature: the lack of a benchmark to assess and
595 compare the previous studies without having to repeat the experiments. To date, each group of collaborating
596 researchers has followed its own path in this regard. Therefore, a series of tests are presented and made
597 public. These can serve as benchmarks for future work so that the performances of different methods can be
598 directly compared.

599 Third, a generalized formulation has been presented. This formulation allows for the modelling of most
600 drayage operation policies. Only those cases in which vehicles can carry more than one container at the same
601 time are excluded. The presented formulation considers locations of vehicles as dummy orders, which allows
602 us to use this formulation in sliding window procedures or in re-optimization due to dynamic information.
603 For this reason, we study the performance of the method in tests with different numbers of orders.

604 Based on this versatile formulation, the effects of policies such as flexible tasks, size of time windows and
605 flexible time windows on the performance of the hauling operation have been analysed. As other studies have
606 previously concluded, the flexibility in the development of orders for the provision and removal of empty
607 containers leads to savings in operational costs.

608 Regarding the flexibility in complying with the time windows, it has been observed that relaxing this re-
609 striction, even including penalty costs, can reduce operating costs and facilitate the management of companies
610 dedicated to haulage.

611 The size of the time window is another aspect that also influences the performance of drayage operations.
612 Obviously, an increase in the length of time windows simplifies the management of drayage companies;
613 however, it would hinder the operations at the terminals, as the influx of containers at their gates would not
614 levelled. The experiments carried out show that, in the case of companies that manage a high number of
615 daily orders, the improvement from very large time windows is less significant.

616 The two previous analyses may help consider mixed policies, where the terminal determines appointments
617 with narrower windows which, however, may be breached incurring penalties. In this manner, access to the
618 terminals would be decongested, but some haulage operators would not be restricted by potential circum-
619 stances. In other words, a policy of narrower windows, which benefits terminal management, but where there
620 is some flexibility in its compliance, could be considered a management strategy that favours both terminals
621 and drayage operators.

622 8. References

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